

LITERATURE AS A SOURCE OF ENCOURAGEMENT IN LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

¹Rakhimova Khilola Kadambaevna, ²Kholmuratova Surayyo Soparmat Qizi

¹Senior lecturer at Foreign Philology faculty, Urgench State University

²Bachelor student of Foreign Philology faculty, Urgench State University

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Abstract. *This article gives information about the aspects of the target language where the literature plays a crucial role as well as the method that can be effectively adopted in the language classes with the usage of authentic materials taken from literary works.*

Keywords: *students, encouragement, source of motivation, literary works, classes, combining language learning and literature.*

To some extent, it is true that nowadays literature is regarded as a less crucial part in terms of learning languages from the point of a plethora of learners' view. Unfortunately, most of them are misled by the idea that language only consists of grammar and lexical resource, yet in order to learn a certain language efficiently, especially English, one has to be willing enough to be involved in reading literature, where he is able to get aware of every concept that language involves. Therefore, this article will look at the concepts of how to encourage students not to only learn a foreign language but also improve their outlook using the social values and beliefs explained only in the literary works of that language.

Why literature?

There is no doubt that language allows us to express our views, emotions together with ideas providing some cases from our experiences, in some matters what we speak shapes the way we are accepted in the society. At this point, one of the critical questions arises; are we able to make others understand and accept our worldview? Are our words enough to describe what we feel clearly? To answer to these questions with total confidence, one has to be a constant reader of literary works, which enable him to consider numerous ways of thinking and hold unbiased perspectives. In other words, literature enables us to use vibrant forms of expression, introduces new ways of thinking with the help of different characters, which give a tremendous opportunity to be somebody else and experience their life in our mind.

Literature in its various forms such as novels and poems is liable to be a profound source of authentic language use, particularly for the students in the beginner level. Unlike grammar books and language learning apps, literature provides us with a glimpse into how words are actually used in daily occasions described in the literary works. This active engagement of students in reading can boost all the linguistic skills accordingly.

Above all, what is extremely crucial in terms of reading literature is developing critical thinking. Reading books in the target language mostly involves students in the analytical process of how to interpret the actions happening there. This process assists them to communicate their ideas and opinions in a clearer way using the target language without any challenges on a consistent reading basis.

Another benefit learner can gain in the reading process is that literature opens a way to understanding a complex cultural world through which it becomes straightforward to interpret the

mentality of other societies, which in turn leads to better analyzing life standards and apply the most suitable ones in our own life.

Hence, students, who are starting a big journey of so-called language learning and are ready to explore the world beyond their thinking, are ought to consider that literature is challenging but highly rewarding experience. After all, understanding very complex sentences in the target language and interpreting them easily can give students a sense of accomplishment, which improves their further curiosity and willingness to stay on a track of gaining proficiency level of the target language.

How to apply in the classes?

A traditional literature class involves the process where a teacher is responsible for retelling the most important parts of a literary work, which is followed by some questions that can arise among the students on the actions happening there. Without any doubt, these lessons can carry a plenty of invaluable knowledge, however, they do not have any power to engage students in the learning process as it is expected. Likewise, the same is likely to be expected from English classes where again teacher-centered approach takes a crucial part of the lesson. Therefore, as a teacher we have to consider how to combine these literature classes with language learning in such engaging way, and ultimately achieve the student confidence in both outlook and language.

One extremely practical method of combining literature and language learning is through the usage of task-based learning, which involves tasks and activities that are likely to encourage learners to utilize the target language on a regular basis throughout the classes discussing real-life topics given in the literary work.

To illustrate, teachers can assign a plethora of tasks to their students such as role-plays, writing a book review, and discussion or debate sections on the main topic of the given literary work. These activities can bring a real-language atmosphere to the class through the high interest students show in the parts where they are able to express their opinion in the target language.

Unluckily, it can be impossible to make a student, who has never been interested in reading, to read a novel from the first attempt. Therefore, it would be a great idea to incorporate some online reading platforms where shorter version in both written and spoken ways are available to chase the information about most frequently used literary works. Through these online tools, students not only gain information but also become engrossed seeing the wide interest users show in those platforms in the form of reviews or competitions they conduct to keep the track of reading. As a result, from a very passive language learner a teacher can establish a very talented one who can analytically think and express own worldview when it comes to the discussion sections.

Furthermore, teachers can benefit a lot from using literary works when they are conducting a lesson aiming at the grammar topic. As soon as the theory is explained, teachers can give a piece of writing that requires the students to write a short review using newly chased complex grammar structures. This activity assists students to chase the grammar topic in a high level, also improves topic-related vocabulary and add accuracy to their writing skills.

All in all, teachers can create a highly dynamic lesson through the usage of task-based approach, some online tools as well as targeted language exercises that brings a plenty of motivation to the students to improve their language proficiency even further.

Conclusion

By way of conclusion, it is worth to admit that literature can serve as a very powerful source of encouragement for language students whose understanding of the world can be broadened by

reading diverse views and experiences outlined in the literary works. In addition, stories become a reminder that readers are not alone in the life challenges and can guide them feel more connected to others, which in turn shapes outstanding features of their target language.

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